

**PREDICTING THE PERFORMANCE
AND FAILURE OF MULTIDIRECTIONAL
POLYMERIC MATRIX COMPOSITE
LAMINATES : A COMBINED MICRO-MACRO
APPROACH**

Ralph J. NUISMER

*University of Utah
Salt Lake city, Utah*

A comprehensive nonlinear ply constitutive theory based on simple micro-mechanics models of failure is summarized and used to predict the stress-strain behavior and failure stress for a number of multidirectional composite laminates subjected to uniaxial tensile stress. In general, it is found that the predicted laminate stress-strain curves are in excellent agreement with the experimental data. The predicted failure stresses show reasonably good agreement with the data, except for two families of laminates for which the strength predictions show consistent errors. Possible explanations of these errors are given and further studies are indicated.

INTRODUCTION

The prediction of the performance and failure of fiber composite laminates is of great importance, both in the optimal use of these materials in present day applications as well as in the development of better composite material systems. In this regard, the progress that has been made in understanding the micro-failure mechanisms that lead to changes in laminate performance and ultimate failure of the laminate is encouraging. Less encouraging, however, has been the inability to combine the qualitative studies of micro-failure mechanisms with continuum models to quantitatively predict this performance and ultimate failure.

Emphasizing here composite laminates subjected to uniform (in-plane) stress states, with few exceptions, e.g. [1,2], quantitative strength predictions have followed the logical approach of basing these predictions on the strength and stiffness properties of the constituent plies. Early approaches to laminate strength prediction used conservative estimates based on "first ply failure". These were followed by a number of attempts at improving the strength predictions by accounting for the loss of stiffness a laminate suffers due to failure of certain of its plies [3,4,5]. And in [6,7] the same approach was extended to predict the strength of laminates containing through the thickness holes and cracks by combining it with the finite element method.

In spite of some notable successes obtained in these studies, it is safe to say that none of these approaches has gained such a level of acceptance that the need for laminate testing has been eliminated. Part of the reason for this appears to be the ad hoc manner in which the ply constitutive equations have been obtained in these studies. However, the primary cause seems to be one of insufficient knowledge of how damage grows both within and between plies, of their interaction with one another, and of their effects on stiffness and strength changes of the laminate. Therefore, it is encouraging that studies of this damage growth have recently been reported, e.g. [8,9,10], which have resulted in a greater understanding of the growth process as well as the beginnings of quantitative predictions.

An avenue of progress in predicting laminate performance and failure would appear to be opened if the micro-failure mechanism studies [8,9,10] could be effectively combined with the macroscopic phenomenological approaches [3,4,5]. A step in this direction was recently taken in [11] where a comprehensive approach was used to develop ply constitutive relations for the damaged as well as undamaged state by combining simplified models of the micro-failure modes within plies with continuum mechanics principles. In the present paper, the constitutive relations developed in [11] are applied to multidirectional laminates of a particular material system to predict their performance and failure under uniaxial tensile loadings. The information provided from this study should help point the way towards future improvements to the model.

THEORETICAL MODEL

In this section, the theoretical model developed in [11] is briefly summarized. Consider first the stress-strain behavior of a composite ply subjected to transverse tensile loading. The stress-strain curve is typically slightly nonlinear until sudden failure takes place, at which time complete separation of the ply occurs. If, however, the ply is stabilized as the 90° ply in a multidirectional laminate, the failure is no longer abrupt. Rather a gradual decrease in the 90° ply stiffness contribution to the laminate takes place due to the growth of matrix cracking (damage). A representation of the stabilized (in situ) 90° ply stress-strain behavior is shown in Fig. 1. It is seen that for a monotonically increasing strain, the stress rises elastically to point A where matrix cracks begin to grow. As matrix cracking continues to grow, the stress rises to maximum value and then begins to decrease steadily. If somewhere along the increasing damage portion of the curve (BCD) the strain is reduced, the stress follows one of the constant damage curves (e.g. OB,OC,OD) from that point. Upon increasing the strain once again, the constant damage curve is followed until the increasing damage curve is reached, at which time the stress again follows

the increasing damage curve. It is observed that this behavior is consistent with that of a cracked elastic body where compliance changes due to a stable growth are occurring.

Fig. 1. Idealized representation of transverse stress vs transverse strain in a stabilized composite ply.

For this simple one-dimensional case, a representation of the entire stress-strain response is given by

$$e = DS(\sigma)\sigma \quad (1)$$

where e and σ are strain and stress, respectively, $S(\sigma)$ is the compliance and

$$D = \|D(e)\|_{\text{sup}} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), $D(e)$ is a monotonically increasing function of strain and $\| \cdot \|_{\text{sup}}$ denotes the maximum value attained by the enclosed function during the entire strain history. D serves as an internal state variable [12], allowing the stress-strain response to be separated into history dependent and history independent parts and giving a measure of the current damage state of the material. Clearly, $D = 1$ implies no damage while $D > 1$ implies that the ply is damaged.

The first step in extending the one-dimensional behavior of Eq. (1) to general plane behavior is to consider physical damage models. Although a wide variety of damage modes are known to occur in composite materials [13], only two idealized models will be considered at this time. Although it is expected that these models will be improved in future studies, they are thought to be sufficient to adequately, if not completely, describe the resulting damaged ply constitutive behavior. The first model, which will be called normal damage, consists of fiber breaks and matrix cracks normal to the fiber direction; the second, which will be called parallel damage, consists of matrix splitting and fiber-matrix debonding. This idealization of physical ply damage as a repetitive array of cracks both normal to and parallel to the fiber direction implies that the basic orthotropic symmetry of the undamaged ply is preserved after damage. Thus, it is not unreasonable to assume the normal-shear interaction on stress-strain behavior and coupling of normal stress effects on normal strain response, observed to be negligible in the undamaged ply [14], remain negligible in the damaged ply as well. Combining these assumptions with the observed

uniaxial stress-strain behavior, as described by Eq. (1), it was postulated in [11] that the general plane constitutive relations of a ply can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} e_1 &= D_1 S_{11}(\sigma_1)\sigma_1 + S_{12}\sigma_2 \\ e_2 &= S_{12}\sigma_1 + D_2 S_{22}(\sigma_2)\sigma_2 \\ e_6 &= D_6 S_{66}(\sigma_6)\sigma_6 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where ply (material symmetry) coordinates and contracted notation are assumed. In Eqs. (3), the undamaged compliances S_{11} , S_{22} , and S_{66} are taken to be, in general, nonlinear functions of the stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_6 , respectively, while S_{12} is taken to be constant due to thermodynamic considerations [11]. In addition, S_{66} is required to be an even function of σ_6 to satisfy the orthotropic symmetry requirements.

To find explicit forms for the damage state variables, D_1 , D_2 and D_6 of Eqs. (3), as functionals of strain history, the following two damage functions for normal and parallel damage are introduced:

$$f_N^2 = \begin{cases} (e_1/e_{1N^*})^2, & e_1 > 0 \\ 0, & e_1 < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$f_P^2 = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{e_1}{D_1 e_{1P^*}} + \frac{e_2}{e_{2^*}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{e_6}{e_{6^*}} \right)^2, & \frac{e_1}{D_1 e_{1P^*}} + \frac{e_2}{e_{2^*}} > 0 \\ \left(\frac{e_6}{e_{6^*}} \right)^2, & \frac{e_1}{D_1 e_{1P^*}} + \frac{e_2}{e_{2^*}} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In Eqs. (4) and (5), e_{1N^*} is the longitudinal ply strain at which normal damage initiates and e_{1P^*} , e_{2^*} and e_{6^*} are the uniaxial longitudinal, transverse, and shear strains, respectively, at which parallel damage initiates. Setting $f_P = 1$, the first of Eqs. (5) is recognized as the strain equivalent of the interactive transverse and shear stress ply failure criterion used in [15] to predict matrix failure of a ply. The D_1 included in the equation reflects the expectation that the Poisson effect of longitudinal strain on transverse stress and, therefore, on matrix splitting should diminish as normal damage grows. The second of Eqs.(5) expresses the expectation that compressive stresses do not contribute to matrix splitting if they are of low magnitude, and differs slightly from that used in [11].

It is next postulated that normal damage initiation and growth in a previously undamaged ply depends only on the value of the damage function f_N . As normal damage grows, it is accompanied by matrix splitting and debonding due to crack blunting effects caused by adjacent fibers. Thus, softening of longitudinal, transverse and shear stiffness is caused, denoted by the monotonically increasing functions $D_1 = D_{1N}(f_N)$, $D_2 = D_{2N}(f_N)$ and $D_6 = D_{6N}(f_N)$. Similarly, it is postulated that parallel damage initiation and growth in a previously undamaged ply depends only on the value of the damage function f_P . Softening of the transverse and shear stiffness is caused, denoted by the monotonically increasing functions $D_2 = D_{2P}(f_P)$ and $D_6 = D_{6P}(f_P)$. Finally, it is assumed that if damage is present from any cause, it will not grow until f_N or f_P become large enough to cause additional softening. This assumption is consistent with the unloading and subsequent reloading behavior exhibited in the uniaxial behavior of Fig. 1. Combining these concepts, leads to the following forms for the damage state variables as functionals of the strain history:

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 &= \|D_1\|_{\text{sup}} \\ D_2 &= \|D_2\|_{\text{sup}} \\ D_6 &= \|D_6\|_{\text{sup}} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In these equations, $\|D_i\|_{sup}$ denotes the maximum value of either $D_{iN}(f_N)$ or $D_{iP}(f_P)$, whichever is greater, obtained in the entire strain history of the laminate. Eqs. (3) and (6) constitute the complete constitutive equations for a composite ply subject to the restriction that compressive stresses do no damage.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Predictions made using the model of constitutive behavior summarized in the preceding section are compared to the experimental results reported in [16]. In this work, stress-strain curves and failure data are given for 21 distinct 8-ply uniaxial tension coupons. The material system used was Thorne1 300/5208 graphite-epoxy, with fiber volume content of all laminates varying by $\pm 2\%$ from a nominal value of 66.4% and a maximum void content of 1.6% by volume. The coupons were instrumented with a single centrally located strain gage rosette, and three coupons were tested for each distinct lamination (except for the $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate for which 6 tests were performed).

Use of the constitutive equations summarized in the preceding section requires the determination of a number of material constants and functions. In particular, four undamaged ply compliances, $S_{11}(\sigma_1)$, S_{12} , $S_{22}(\sigma_2)$, $S_{66}(\sigma_6)$, four damage initiation strains, e_{1N}^* , e_{1P}^* , e_2^* , e_6^* , and five damage state functions, $D_{iN}(f_N)$, $D_{2N}(f_N)$, $D_{6N}(f_N)$, $D_{2P}(f_P)$, $D_{6P}(f_P)$, must be determined.

The four undamaged ply compliances are represented using polynomial fits of the 0° longitudinal stress versus longitudinal and transverse strain curves shown in Fig. 2, the 90° longitudinal stress versus longitudinal strain curve shown in Fig. 3, and the 0° shear stress versus shear strain curve shown in Fig. 4. Unfortunately, no compressive longitudinal or transverse stress versus strain curves are available in [16] since this data is needed to fully represent the multidirectional coupon stress-strain curves. Thus, in the present case, the 0° compressive longitudinal stress versus longitudinal strain curve is assumed to be linear with slope identical to that in tension while the compressive transverse stress versus transverse strain curve is assumed to be nonlinear. The latter curve has been approximated by assuming the nonlinearity to be similar to that of the Hercules AS/3501-5 material system [17] but proportioned upward in stiffness to make the initial compressive modulus identical to that in tension. The final polynomial fits are given by

$$\begin{aligned} S_{11}(\sigma_1) &= 6.334 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (MPa)}^{-1} \\ S_{12} &= -1.881 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (MPa)}^{-1} \\ S_{22}(\sigma_2) &= \begin{cases} 8.844 \times 10^{-5} \text{ (MPa)}^{-1}, & \sigma_2 > 0 \\ 8.844 \times 10^{-5} - 2.486 \times 10^{-8} \sigma_2 + 7.017 \times 10^{-11} \sigma_2^2 \text{ (MPa)}^{-1}, & \sigma_2 < 0 \end{cases} \quad (7) \\ S_{66}(\sigma_6) &= 1.784 \times 10^{-4} - 1.057 \times 10^{-6} |\sigma_6| + 4.323 \times 10^{-8} \sigma_6^2 \text{ (MPa)}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Three of the four damage initiation strains are obtained directly from the three basic ply stress-strain curves, Figs. 2-4. Thus, e_{1N}^* , e_2^* and e_6^* are obtained as the average failure strains in longitudinal tension, transverse tension, and shear, respectively. The remaining damage initiation strain, e_{1P}^* , is determined as the uniaxial longitudinal strain (e_1 with $e_2 = e_6 = 0$) that results in a transverse tensile stress in the ply equal to the transverse failure stress (49.6 MPa). The values used in subsequent predictions are

$$\begin{aligned} e_{1N}^* &= .0098 & e_2^* &= .0044 \\ e_{1P}^* &= .0144 & e_6^* &= .0273 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It is noted here that, in general, the damage initiation strains are dependent on laminate orientation and stacking sequence [8-10]. In the current study, this dependence has been ignored. However, the stacking sequences used in the experimental program of [16] are relatively interleaved rather than clumped which should help to minimize errors introduced by this effect.

The five damage state functions are the least straightforward to determine. That is, because the unloading behavior of a damaged ply is unstable unless load transfer from adjacent plies is provided, the damage state functions must be determined indirectly from multidirectional laminate tests or by using theoretical micro-mechanics models of damage growth in plies. In the present study, the indirect testing approach is combined with a simple crack compliance model to determine the damage state functions.

In the present study, the exact nature of the damage state functions D_{1N} , D_{2N} and D_{6N} (essentially softening due to fiber failure) plays an insignificant role. This is because fiber failure either does not occur before the ultimate failure of the tensile coupon, or because when it does occur it immediately precipitates ultimate failure. Thus, for the present study it is sufficient to ignore the details of fiber failure unloading as long it occurs rapidly. It is noted that in specimens of more general geometry, such as those containing through-the-thickness holes or slots where local fiber failure near the stress concentration can occur prior to ultimate failure of the specimen, the details of this unloading process could be very significant and should, therefore, be modeled more appropriately.

The damage state functions D_{2p} and D_{6p} (essentially softening due to matrix cracking and debonding) must be determined accurately since matrix damage and subsequent unloading of the ply play a significant role in the present study. The first of these, $D_{2p}(f_p)$, is determined indirectly from the $(90^\circ/0^\circ/2/90^\circ)_S$ stress-strain curves shown in Fig. 15. In this procedure, the 90° unloading behavior is obtained by subtracting the undamaged 0° stress-strain behavior from that of the laminate using laminated plate theory. It is found that assuming the damage function D_{2p} to be an exponential function provides a good fit of the unloading, signifying an initially rapid loss in stiffness followed by a more gradual decline. This seems appropriate in view of studies such as [10] that indicate matrix cracks tend to appear suddenly with a certain characteristic spacing and then grow more densely spaced as the load (or strain) increases. An estimate for the damage state function D_{6p} was obtained from a consideration of energy release rates and crack compliance relationships for a finite length Griffith crack in an infinite orthotropic material [18]. For the T300/5208 material system, a ratio of compliance change in transverse tension to compliance change in shear of 3.74 was found to result from an increment of self-similar crack growth parallel to the fiber direction. Although this model assumes noninteraction of adjacent matrix cracks, this is not a serious drawback because essentially the same assumption is used in predicting matrix crack spacing [8, 10]. A more serious error is expected from ignoring finite width effects, however. Although it seems clear that further work is needed in this area, the functions used to represent the damage state functions in the present study are given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{1N} &= e^{7.0(f_N-1)} & , & & f_N > 1 \\
 D_{2N} &= e^{7.0(f_N-1)} & , & & f_N > 1 \\
 D_{6N} &= e^{7.0(f_N-1)} & , & & f_N > 1
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

$$D_{2P} = \begin{cases} e^{1.6(f_p-1)} & , \quad \frac{e_1}{D_1 e_{1P}^*} + \frac{e_2}{e_2^*} > 0, f_p > 1 \\ 1 & , \quad \frac{e_1}{D_1 e_{1P}^*} + \frac{e_2}{e_2^*} < 0, f_p > 1 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$D_{6P} = e^{-2.4(f_p-1)} \quad , \quad f_p > 1$$

The two values shown for D_{2P} reflect the expectation that matrix splitting will not result in significant softening of the compressive transverse stress-strain behavior under the low compressive load assumption used in the development of the constitutive equations [11].

COMPARISON OF MODEL AND EXPERIMENT

The material constants and functions of the preceding section, Eqs. (7-9), were used in a computer program (UNIFAIL) developed to numerically predict laminate stress-strain behavior, damage growth, and ultimate failure. UNIFAIL uses laminated plate theory and the ply constitutive behavior developed in [11] to predict the performance of laminates subjected to uniform in-plane stresses. A standard incremental-iterative solution approach similar to that outlined in [11] is necessitated by the nonlinear path-dependent nature of the ply constitutive relations.

It is clear that the uniform stress state assumed in each ply of the laminate by UNIFAIL is an approximation to the actual state of stress experienced by the test coupons. However, away from the end tabs and free edges, near the center of the specimens where the strain gages are applied, the approximation is quite appropriate unless substantial delamination of a coupon occurs. The failure of the coupons is a different matter, however, since failure may be initiated near the free edges and then progress in toward the center. It is clear that UNIFAIL cannot account for such failures and, in such cases, is expected to give poor predictions.

In Figs. 5-21, the longitudinal stress versus both longitudinal and transverse strain curves to failure are shown for 17 distinct multidirectional laminate uniaxial tension coupons along with the predicted performance from UNIFAIL. In all Figs. 2-21, the dashed curves show the approximate bounds of the test data reported in [16], while the solid curves show the predicted results. An arrow at the end of a predicted curve signifies that the curve continues on. Although predicted curves are shown in Figs. 2-4, these figures represent basic ply data so that the predicted curves are simply curve fits.

The first set of laminates to be considered is the $(\pm\theta)_{2S}$ family of laminates, Figs. 5-9. From these figures, it is observed that both the predicted longitudinal and transverse strain curves lie within the observed data scatter bands with the exception of the longitudinal strain curve of the $(\pm 75^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate. Also, with the exception of the $(\pm 15^\circ)_{2S}$ and $(\pm 75^\circ)_{2S}$ laminates, the predicted failure stresses show reasonable agreement with those observed. The predicted and observed failure stresses for this set of laminates are summarized in Table 1, along with ply stress information helpful in the discussion of the results. In Table 1, the stresses in only the $+0$ ply are shown since the stresses in the -0 ply are identical with the exception of a sign change in the shear stress. The column headed Initial Ply Stress Ratio shows the ratio of ply stresses in ply coordinates predicted by UNIFAIL to the applied uniaxial tension stress, σ_0 , for very small applied loads (linear). The last two columns show the ultimate stress predicted by UNIFAIL and the average value observed in the tests.

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(0^\circ)_8$ laminate.

Fig. 3. Stress-strain curve for uniaxial tension of a $(90^\circ)_8$ laminate.

Fig. 4. Stress-strain curve for simple shear of a (0°) laminate.

Fig. 5. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(\pm 15^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate.

Fig. 6. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(\pm 30^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate.

Fig. 7. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate.

Fig. 8. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(\pm 60^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate.

Fig. 9. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(\pm 75^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate.

Laminate	Ply	Initial Ply Stress Ratio			Failure Stress (MPa)	
		σ_1/σ_0	σ_2/σ_0	σ_6/σ_0	UNIFAIL	Test
$(\pm 15^\circ)_{2S}$	+15°	1.052	-0.052	-0.043	1448	733
$(\pm 30^\circ)_{2S}$	+30°	1.136	-0.136	-0.210	490	471
$(\pm 45^\circ)_{2S}$	+45°	0.917	0.083	-0.500	152	152
$(\pm 60^\circ)_{2S}$	+60°	0.384	0.617	-0.510	69	66
$(\pm 75^\circ)_{2S}$	+75°	0.077	0.923	-0.268	52	42

Table 1. Ply stresses and failure stresses for $(\pm\theta)_{2S}$ laminates.

The poor correlation between the predicted longitudinal stress-longitudinal strain curve of the $(\pm 75^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate and that observed in the tests is unexplained. However, it is noted here and in [16] that this experimental stress-strain data exhibits strange behavior initially as well as considerable scatter, making the data somewhat suspect. This view is reinforced by the fact that UNIFAIL predicts the stress-strain behavior accurately for all other laminates shown in Figs. 5-21, including the longitudinal stress-transverse strain curve of the $(\pm 75^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate.

Ultimate failure of all laminates shown in Table 1, with the exception of the $(\pm 15^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate, is predicted to occur due to the onset of matrix damage in both plies. Failure of the $(\pm 15^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate, on the other hand, is predicted to occur due to fiber failure of both plies. In fact, inspection of Table 1 indicates that the predicted ply stresses at the test failure load of 733 MPa are of such low magnitude that no reasonable failure criterion (including the tensor polynomial [19]) accounts for ply failure at that load level. It is suspected that the poor failure stress prediction for the $(\pm 15^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate is the result of substantial free edge effects on the state of stress. Similar conclusions on the importance of the free edge effect on the failure of angle ply laminates with $\theta < 45^\circ$ were reported in [15] and [20]. Using a simple analysis of the in-plane stresses in each ply at the free edge of the coupon, it was shown in [20] that the effect of the free-edge on in-plane ply stresses was to promote matrix failure of the ply in this region. For a particular graphite-epoxy material system, this effect was especially pronounced in angle plies with smaller orientation angles (say $\theta < 25^\circ$). A simple calculation similar to that in [20] reveals that for the present material system the same conclusion may be reached. Thus, although for the $(\pm 30^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate failure of the ply matrix at the free edge is predicted to occur at 83% of the load needed to cause matrix failure of a ply in the interior of the laminate, for the $(\pm 15^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate this ratio is only 42%. Since the in-plane stress perturbation is known to decay rapidly away from the free edge [20], it is expected that ply failure across the entire coupon width, which results in ultimate failure of the coupon, will take place at higher loads than the percentages indicated by the simple free edge calculations done here. Therefore, it appears likely that free edge effects on failure will be of importance here only for the $(\pm 15^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate, thus explaining the poor failure prediction obtained for this laminate. The relatively poor failure prediction for the $(\pm 75^\circ)_{2S}$ laminate resists a totally satisfactory explanation. Although more will be said subsequently concerning the failure of this laminate, the rather strange behavior of its stress-strain data is recalled and it is noted that the ultimate stress for this laminate (42.1 MPa) is lower than that of the $(90^\circ)_8$ laminate (49.6 MPa).

Considering next the $(0^\circ/\pm\theta/0^\circ)_S$ family of laminates, Figs. 10-15, it is seen that all stress-strain predictions lie within the scatter bands of the experimental data. Failure stress predictions are in reasonable agreement with the test values with the exception of the $(0^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ and $(0^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminates. The predicted and observed failure stresses and the predicted ply stresses are summarized in Table 2, where the column headings have the same interpretation as in Table 1.

Fig. 10. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(0^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 11. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(0^\circ/\pm 30^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 12. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 13. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(0^\circ/\pm 60^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 14. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(0^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 15. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(90^\circ/0^\circ_2/90^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 16. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(90^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 17. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(90^\circ/\pm 30^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 18. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 19. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(90^\circ/\pm 60^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 20. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(90^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Fig. 21. Stress-strain curves for uniaxial tension of a $(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate.

Laminate	Ply	Initial Ply Stress Ratio			Failure Stress(MPa)	
		σ_1/σ_0	σ_2/σ_0	σ_6/σ_0	UNIFAIL	Test
$(0^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/0^\circ)_S$	0°	1.085	-0.028	0	1413	1070
	+15°	0.965	-0.022	-0.032		
$(0^\circ/\pm 30^\circ/0^\circ)_S$	0°	1.406	-0.072	0	1055	970
	+30°	0.703	-0.036	-0.088		
$(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ)_S$	0°	1.741	-0.049	0	855	877
	+45°	0.283	0.026	-0.105		
$(0^\circ/\pm 60^\circ/0^\circ)_S$	0°	1.853	-0.002	0	807	726
	+60°	0.058	0.090	-0.075		
$(0^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/0^\circ)_S$	0°	1.868	0.026	0	786	559
	+75°	-0.017	0.123	-0.036		
$(90^\circ/0^\circ_2/90^\circ)_S$	0°	1.868	0.034	0	786	824
	90°	-0.034	0.132	0		

Table 2. Ply stresses and failure stresses for $(0^\circ/\pm\theta/0^\circ)_S$ laminates.

Ultimate failure of all laminates shown in Table 2 is predicted to occur due to fiber failure of the 0° plies. No damage is predicted to occur prior to ultimate failure for the first three laminates of Table 2, while matrix failure of the $\pm\theta$ plies is predicted to occur prior to ultimate failure for each of the last three laminates. As seen in Figs. 13-15, the matrix damage prior to ultimate failure produces a distinct "knee" only for the longitudinal stress-transverse strain curve of the $(90^\circ/0^\circ_2/90^\circ)_S$ laminate.

As in the case of the $(\pm 15^\circ)_2S$ laminate, the poor failure prediction for the $(0^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate is felt to be the result of free edge effects on the failure process which cannot be accounted for by UNIFAIL. The poor failure prediction for the $(0^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate is unexplained. It is noticed that the test failure stress for this laminate, as well as for the $(0^\circ/\pm 60^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminate, is below that of the $(90^\circ/0^\circ_2/90^\circ)_S$ laminate, and both are less than that expected if the $\pm\theta$ plies contributed nothing to the strength of the laminate (772 MPa). Thus, it appears that the $\pm\theta$ plies actively contribute to the failure of the 0° plies in these two laminates. Why this would occur for these laminates and not for the $(90^\circ/0^\circ_2/90^\circ)_2$ laminate is not clear.

Considering next the $(90^\circ/\pm\theta/90^\circ)_S$ family of laminates, Figs. 16-20, it is seen that all stress-strain predictions lie within the scatter bands of the experimental data. Predicted failure stresses are good for the $(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ and $(90^\circ/\pm 60^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminates, but poor for the $(90^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/90^\circ)_S$, $(90^\circ/\pm 30^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ and $(90^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminates. The predicted and observed failure stresses and the predicted ply stresses are summarized in Table 3, where the column headings have the same interpretation as in Tables 1 and 2.

In all laminates of the $(90^\circ/\pm\theta/90^\circ)_S$ family, the 90° plies are the first to suffer matrix damage, followed by matrix damage to the $\pm\theta$ plies in all but the first laminate of Table 3 in which the $\pm\theta$ plies suffer fiber failure. In either case, failure of the $\pm\theta$ plies immediately precipitates final failure of the laminate.

Laminate	Ply	Initial Ply Stress Ratio			Failure Stress (MPa)	
		σ_1/σ_0	σ_2/σ_0	σ_6/σ_0	UNIFAIL	TEST
$(90^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/90^\circ)_S$	90°	-0.147	0.147	0	689	459
	+15°	1.961	0.039	-0.041		
$(90^\circ/\pm 30^\circ/90^\circ)_S$	90°	-0.512	0.213	0	483	276
	+30°	2.226	0.073	-0.114		
$(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$	90°	-1.084	0.405	0	172	169
	+45°	2.455	0.223	-0.255		
$(90^\circ/\pm 60^\circ/90^\circ)_S$	90°	-1.204	0.758	0	69	77
	+60°	1.844	0.602	-0.381		
$(90^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/90^\circ)_S$	90°	-0.426	0.974	0	52	34
	+75°	0.527	0.925	-0.256		
$(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ)_S$	90°	-0.756	0.169	0	558	525
	+45°	0.917	0.083	-0.121		
	0°	2.589	-0.003	0		

Table 3. Ply stresses and failure stresses for $(90^\circ/\pm\theta/90^\circ)_S$ and $(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ)_S$ laminates.

As in the other laminates containing $\pm 15^\circ$ plies, the poor failure prediction for the $(90^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate is attributed to free edge effects on failure. The poor failure prediction for the $(90^\circ/\pm 30^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate may also be due to free edge effects, even though no evidence of such effects was present in the previous laminates containing $\pm 30^\circ$ plies. However, unlike the first two laminates containing $\pm 30^\circ$ plies, substantial interlaminar shear is present in the $(90^\circ/\pm 30^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate in both the longitudinal and transverse directions. Further work on analyzing the effect of free edges on laminate strength is clearly necessary.

As with the two previous laminates containing $\pm 75^\circ$ plies, the $(90^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminate exhibits an observed ultimate stress below that of the basic 90° ply (49.6 MPa). The reason for this is not clear. If, indeed, the data is valid, it seems that three possible reasons for the poor prediction exist: free edge effects; compression stress in the fiber direction of the 90° plies; or residual stress effects. However, free edge effects are small for this laminate (as they are also for the other two laminates containing $\pm 75^\circ$ plies) compared to others that seemingly suffered no ill effects from the presence of free edges. Compression in the 90° plies especially after they have experienced matrix damage, could lead to a softening in the longitudinal stiffness of these plies, as suggested in [7], and, perhaps, early failure. However, this is not evidenced in the $(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ or $(90^\circ/\pm 60^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminates in which the 90° ply longitudinal compressive stresses are considerably higher (see Table 3). Also, predictions from UNIFAIL with various amounts of softening in 90° longitudinal compression after matrix damage occurs yield poor fits of the stress-strain data for all laminates where longitudinal compression in the 90° plies is a factor. Finally, upon consideration of the characteristic damage spacing of matrix cracks, which is on the order of several ply thicknesses [8,10], and the support provided the cracked ply from adjacent plies, it is difficult to see how substantial softening could occur. Residual stress effects on laminate failure can be appreciable in some cases [21] and are presently not accounted for in UNIFAIL. Although this may serve to explain the low failure stresses observed for the $(\pm 75^\circ)_2S$ and $(90^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ laminates, it is not clear how this explains the low strength of the $(0^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/0^\circ)_2$ laminate where failure is dominated by the 0° plies.

The last laminate considered is the quasi-isotropic ($90^\circ/45^\circ/0^\circ$)_S laminate, Fig. 21. From this figure, it is seen that both predicted stress-strain curves lie within the scatter bands of the data, and that the failure stress prediction shows reasonably good agreement with the test value, see also Table 3. Matrix damage occurs first in this laminate in the 90° plies, followed by matrix failure of the 45° plies just prior to ultimate failure which occurs due to fiber failure in the 0° plies. It is noted that although substantial interlaminar shear stresses are present in this laminate at failure, the interlaminar normal stress along the center plane of the coupon is compressive due to the stacking sequence chosen [16]. This appears to have eliminated free edge effects on this set of coupons.

DISCUSSION

A comprehensive nonlinear constitutive theory developed in [11] to describe the in-plane stress-strain behavior of both damaged and undamaged composite plies has been used in the present work to predict the stress-strain behavior and failure stress for a number of multidirectional composite laminates subjected to uniaxial tensile stresses. In general, it was found that the predicted laminate stress-strain curves were in excellent agreement with the experimental data for all 17 laminates considered. With consistent exceptions, the predicted failure stresses showed reasonably good agreement with the observed failure stresses. The exceptions consisted of all laminates containing $\pm 15^\circ$ plies and all laminates containing $\pm 75^\circ$ plies. While the high failure stress predictions obtained for all laminates containing $\pm 15^\circ$ plies seem satisfactorily explained as a consequence of free edge effects on failure, no entirely satisfactory reason was determined for the consistently low failure stress predictions for the laminates containing $\pm 75^\circ$ plies. Although the results obtained in the present study are encouraging, it seems clear that further studies are necessary in which the effects of out-of-plane stresses and residual stresses on failure are included. These studies are forthcoming.

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